

**Design, Synthesis, Characterization, Integrated SAR and Molecular
Docking Studies of Sulphonamide-Derived Indole-2-one Schiff's Bases
Potential Anticancer and Antibacterial Agent**

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Abstract

Indole-2,3-dione (isatin) and its derivatives have gained considerable attention owing to their broad spectrum of biological activities, particularly anticancer and antibacterial properties. In view of the increasing resistance to existing antimicrobial agents and the urgent need for novel anticancer therapeutics, the present study focuses on the synthesis, characterization, and biological evaluation of a series of novel sulphonamide-containing indole-2-one Schiff's bases (7a–7j). The synthesized compounds were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*) bacteria, as well as for anticancer activity against human cancer cell lines. Compounds 7a, 7c, and 7j exhibited significant antibacterial activity, while compounds 7b and 7c demonstrated acceptable anticancer activity; the remaining derivatives showed moderate biological efficacy. To further understand the binding interactions and possible mechanism of action, molecular docking studies were carried out using the Schrödinger Suite. Compound 7b displayed a high docking score of -9.729 with a binding energy of -42.828 kcal/mol, whereas compounds 7c, 7e, and 7j also exhibited strong binding affinities with docking scores of -9.238 , -8.438 , and -9.823 , respectively, outperforming the standard drug. The docking scores of the newly developed compounds ranged from -8.512 to -3.142 . Hydrogen-bond interactions were limited and observed primarily for compounds 7e (GLY 521), 7i (LEU 525), 7j (ASP 351), and 7f (ASP 351), while significant hydrophobic interactions involving residues ARG 394 and TRP 383 contributed to ligand stabilization for several compounds. Overall, the combined biological and in silico results suggest that sulphonamide-based indole-2-one Schiff's bases represent promising lead structures for the development of novel antibacterial and anticancer agents.

KEYWORDS: Indole, Schiff's bases, Sulphonamide, Anticancer, Antibacterial, Docking, Dock score,

1. Introduction:

Indole-2,3-dione(Isatin) compounds and its derivatives had intense interest because of having anticancer activity against various cancer cell lines like MCF-7, SKVO3 e.t.c and their *in vivo* activity efficacy in Human cancer cell lines. More over its analogs contain sulphur hetero atoms are having antibacterial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and their *in vivo* chemotherapeutic efficacy. Further advances in development of Isatin analogs are likely to provide better compounds for clinical use. Because resistance to antimicrobial drugs is widespread, new antimicrobial and understanding of their mechanisms of action are vital. The development of antibacterial resistance and anticancer active molecules are as created the need for an efficient synthesis of Indole-2-one derivatives can be easily adapted toward the assembly of Indole-2-one based antibacterial and anticancer drugs¹⁻¹⁸.

2. Review of Literature:

2.1. Anti-cancer activity:

Hasan Kucukbay and coworkers¹⁹ has reported synthesis and anticancer properties of novel hydrazone derivatives incorporating pyridine and isatin moieties. Nine novel hydrazone derivatives incorporating pyridine and isatin moieties were synthesized through one-pot, four-component heterocyclic condensation reactions. The structures of all new compounds were identified by ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), ¹³C NMR, and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopic techniques and elemental analysis. Cell viability assays for the tested hydrazone derivatives were performed and the log IC₅₀ values of the compounds were calculated after a 24-h treatment. Compound(**Fig:1**) showed high cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 cells as compared with docetaxel ($p < .05$). Whereas the log IC₅₀ of docetaxel was 0.2400 μ M for MCF-7 cells at 24 h, the log IC₅₀ values of compounds 4b, 4d, and 4i were -0.1293, -0.1700, and 0.2459 μ M, respectively.

Fig 1 : Structure of Compound

Sergey N. Lavrenov and coworkers²⁰ has reported the synthesis and study of cytotoxic activity of novel 3,3-bis(indol-3-yl)-1,3-dihydroindol-2-ones. A series of 3,3-bis(indol-3-yl)-1,3-dihydroindol-2-ones (**Fig : 2**) containing substituents at different positions of the oxindole ring were synthesized to study the effect of the position of the substituent on biological activity. Some of the new derivatives showed high *in vitro* cytotoxic activity (MTT assay) on human tumor cell lines and lower (60 and 150 times less) cytotoxicity on donor human fibroblasts compared to doxorubicin.

Fig 2: Structure of Novel 3,3-bis(indol-3-yl)-1,3-dihydroindol-2-ones

2.2 Anticonvulsant activity:

Saravanan and coworkers²¹ reported the anti-convulsant activity of novel 1-(morpholinomethyl)-3-substituted isatin derivatives (**Fig:3**). Among the synthesized compounds, isoxazole-substituted isatin derivatives exhibit better activity than the corresponding acryloylphenylimino-substituted isatin derivatives. The increase in the activity

may be due to the presence of an extra electron donor atom (D) on the isoxazole ring, which might be responsible for additional bonding with the binding site.

Fig 3 : Structure of Novel 1-(morpholinomethyl)-3-substituted isatin derivatives

2.3. Antitumor activity:

Hatem A. Abdel-Aziz and coworkers²² prepared a new series of benzene sulfonamide derivatives incorporating pyrazole and isatin moieties. Biological evaluation of the target compounds was performed against the metalloenzyme carbonic anhydrase (CA, EC 4.2.1.1) and more precisely against the human isoforms hCA I, II (cytosolic), IX and XII (transmembrane, tumor-associated enzymes). Most of the tested compounds efficiently inhibited hCA I, II and IX, with KIs of 2.5- 102 nM, being more effective than the reference drug acetazolamide. Compounds **(4.1)** and **(4.2)**, with 5-NO₂ substitution on the isatin ring, were found to be selective inhibitors of hCA IX and hCA XII. Docking studies revealed that the NO₂ group of both compounds participate in interactions with Asp132 within the hCA IX active site, and with residues Lys67 and Asp130 in hCA XII, respectively.

Fig 4 : Structure of benzene sulfonamide derivatives incorporating Pyrazole and Isatin moieties (4.1 and 4.2)

2.4. Antidiabetic activity:

Fazal Rahim and coworkers²³ were carried out worked on isatin base Schiff bases (1-20) were synthesized, characterized by ¹HNMR and EI/MS and evaluated for α -glucosidase inhibitory potential. Out of these twenty (20) compounds only six analogs showed potent α -glucosidase inhibitory potential with IC₅₀ value ranging in between 2.2 ± 0.25 to $83.5 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{M}$ when compared with the standard acarbose (IC₅₀ = $840 \pm 1.73 \mu\text{M}$). Among the series compound (**Fig 5**) having IC₅₀ value ($18.3 \pm 0.56 \mu\text{M}$), 9 ($83.5 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{M}$), 11 ($3.3 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{M}$), 12 ($2.2 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{M}$), 14 ($11.8 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{M}$), and 20 ($3.0 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{M}$) showed excellent inhibitor potential many fold better than the standard acarbose. The binding interactions of these active analogs were confirmed through molecular docking.

Fig 5: Structure of Isatin based Schiff bases

Based on the designed scheme and above literature, synthesis is carried out and spectral analysis is performed to characterize the synthetic compounds; Later evaluated for pharmacological activity and results are tabulated in individual tables and detailed methodology was given in Chapter-I

3. Design of Present studies based on Literature Review

Based on literature Review, Indole-2,3-dione (Isatin) compounds and its derivatives had intense interest because of having anticancer activity against various cancer cell lines like MCF-7, SKVO3 e.t.c and their *in vivo* activity efficacy in Human cancer cell lines. More over its analogs contain sulphur hetero atoms are having antibacterial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and their *in vivo* chemotherapeutic efficacy. Further advances in development of Isatin analogs are likely to provide better compounds for clinical use. Because resistance to antimicrobial

drugs is widespread, new antimicrobial and understanding of their mechanisms of action are vital. The development of antibacterial resistance and anticancer active molecules are as created the need for an efficient synthesis of Indole-2-one derivatives can be easily adapted toward the assembly of Indole-2-one based antibacterial and anticancer drugs.

Keeping in view the potential biological activities of Indole-2-one, sulphonamide and imine linkage, all the moieties are synergized in a single nucleus in the current research (**Fig: 6**). The novel hybrids thus obtained are likely to possess significant biological activities.

Fig:6. Design strategy for sulphonamide linked Indole-2-one derivatives

Fig 7: Schematic representation of Synthesis of sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases(7a-7j).

4. Experimental Section.

4.1 Present work: General Procedure:

Step-I: Synthesis of 1-Benzylidinone 2,3-dione(N-benzyl Isatin)(3a-3j):

Take substituted indole-2,3-dione(**1a-1h**)-3.37mM and an equal portion of substituted benzyl chloride (**2a-2b**) (3.70 mM), combine with 20ml of N,N Dimethyl formamide and then add 2.0 gm of K₂CO₃. Once the reaction mixture was gently mixed, reflux it for 2 hrs, let it cool and add it to 100 ml of ice cold water. After drying and recrystallizing from acetonitrile, the resultant orange red precipitate of 1-Benzylidinone 2,3-dione derivatives(**3a-3j**) was obtained.

Step-II: Synthesis of Para substituted benzenesulphonamide derivatives(6a-6j):

Substituted Hydrazine hydrate (**5**) (0.05mole) was taken in 25 ml of DMF and P-substituted benzene sulphonyl chloride (**4a-4b**) (0.01 mole) was added and refluxed for a period of 2 hrs. To obtain the para substituted benzenesulphonamide derivatives(**6a-6j**), the mixture was poured in to the cracked ice and filtered, and recrystallized with alcohol.

Step-III: Synthesis of Sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases derivatives(7a-7j):

Equimolar amount of N-substituted Isatin derivatives (0.01mol)(**3a-3j**) and Para substituted benzenesulphonamide derivatives (**6a-6j**) (0.01mol) were combined and dissolved in 20ml of ethanol before being refluxed at the rate of 2-3hrs with a little/few drops of (2ml) acid (glacial CH₃COOH) . TLC at n-Hexane/EtoAc(7:3) was used to keep a track of the reaction's development. After being brought to ambient temperature, the resultant was placed in refrigerator over-night to induce the solid formation. After being filtered out and recrystallized from methanol ,a crystalline solid of Sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases (**7a-7j**).

Newly synthesized Sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases (7a-7j) were prepared in three steps. In Step-I, substituted isatin undergoing n-benylation with benzyl/4-methyl benzyl chloride to give a n-benzyl isatin(1a-1h). In Step-II, 4-substituted benzene sulphonyl chloride reacts with hydrazine hydrate to form compound 2a-2b, then followed by Schiff's base reaction with compound 1a-1h in step-3 to give the title derivatives (7a to 7j).

All the synthesized final target structures were confirmed by IR, ^1H NMR and Mass spectral data. All of the compounds had aromatic -CH stretching frequencies at 3000-3100 cm^{-1} and aliphatic C-H stretching frequencies around 2998-2715 cm^{-1} , according to IR spectral data. The existence of SO_2 stretching in sulphonamide groups indicated by the prominent absorption peak seen between 1210-1298 cm^{-1} presence of. Detected a single distinct carbonyl group (C=O) absorption peak at about 1700-1728 cm^{-1} . Most compounds with 'C-C' stretching of Aro- ring at 1482 and 1535 cm^{-1} respectively. Some of the compounds exhibit an absorption peak ranging at 765-843 cm^{-1} denoting C-Cl stretching. In ^1H NMR(DMSO- d_6) spectrum analysis of sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases showing single peak around at δ 9.501-9.985 for benzyl protons and also showed single peak around at δ 9.002-9.437 for -NH protons. All the target molecules distinctly exhibit singlet, doublet and triplet states for aromatic protons at δ 8.453-6.894. Hardly very few compounds are showed at δ 2.305-1.853 (singlet) for methyl group (Aromatic- CH_3).

Fig.8: Sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases (7a-7j)

4.2. Pharmacological Activity.

4.2.1. Anticancer activity:

All the synthesized target molecules were screened by MTT assay protocol against MCF-7 cancer cell line. From these results (Table 4.1), the IC_{50} values are ranged between **23.83 μ g** to **61.31 μ g**, the compounds **7b(23.83 μ g)** and **7c(24.66 μ g)** **7e(27.68 μ g)** showed good anticancer activity and remaining compounds were showed tolerable activity against MCF7 cell line. These all results were compared with Doxorubicin as a standard drug. The obtained results were presented in the **table 4.1** and expressed as a **mean \pm SEM** of each single concentrations. The compounds are perpetually active via those with Schiff's bases of sulphonamide containing "indole-2-oneskeleton" and the presence of lipophilic and "EWG(-Cl, -CH₃)" in the aromatic ring of Isatin moieties is advantageous.

Table 1. Anticancer activity- IC_{50} values of the tested compounds against MCF-7 cancer cell lines.

S. No	Sample Name	IC_{50} (μ g)(MCF-7)
1	7a	61.31 \pm 0.109
2	7b	23.83\pm0.152
3	7c	24.66\pm0.032
4	7e	37.43 \pm 0.216
5	7j	27.68\pm0.109
6	Doxorubicin	16.32\pm0.102

Fig.9: Graphically represented Anticancer activity of novel Indole-2-one linked Schiff's bases(7a, 7b, 7c, 7e, 7j).

Table.2 Raw data for calculating the IC₅₀ values for 7a, 7b, 7c, 7e & 7j

5	0.598	11.7	88.2	61.31± 0.109
10	0.509	24.92	75.07	
25	0.486	28.31	71.68	
50	0.362	46.6	53.39	
100	0.198	70.79	29.2	
	0.678	0	100	
	0	0	0	

5	0.412	39.23	60.76	23.82± 0.152
10	0.379	44.1	55.89	
25	0.303	55.3	44.69	
50	0.276	59.29	40.7	
100	0.123	81.85	18.14	
	0.678	0	100	
	0	0	0	

7c:Concentration(μg)	Absorbance at 570nm	% Inhibition	% Viability	IC ₅₀
5	0.564	16.81	83.18	24.66 \pm 0.03
10	0.334	50.73	49.27	2
25	0.256	62.24	37.75	
50	0.187	72.41	27.58	
100	0.102	84.95	15.04	
Untreated	0.678	0	100	
Blank	0	0	0	

7e:Concentration(μg)	Absorbance at 570nm	% Inhibition	% Viability	IC ₅₀
5	0.51	24.77	75.22	37.43 \pm 0.21
10	0.443	34.66	65.33	6
25	0.354	47.78	52.21	
50	0.224	66.96	33.03	
100	0.154	77.28	22.71	
Untreated	0.678	0	100	
Blank	0	0	0	

7j:Concentration(μg)	Absorbance at 570nm	% Inhibition	% Viability	IC ₅₀
5	0.543	19.09	80.08	27.68 \pm 0.10
10	0.325	52.06	47.93	9
25	0.298	56.04	43.95	
50	0.203	70.05	29.94	
100	0.176	74.04	25.95	
Untreated	0.678	0	100	
Blank	0	0	0	

Fig.10 Graphical representation of anticancer activity of novel Schiff's bases of Indole-2-one derivatives (7a, 7b, 7c, 7e, 7j).-IC₅₀ values

4.2.2. Antibacterial Activity:

Using Agar well diffusion method the synthetic compounds *invitro* antimicrobial activity was evaluated against variety of pathogenic reference bacterial strains and the results to this regard are summarised in (Table:3). GP bacterial strains -[*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*] and GN bacterial strains -[*Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella paratyphi*] used to test the synthesized compounds *invitro* antibacterial properties. Streptomycin as a standard control to compare the zone of inhibition and to determine the antibacterial activity.

The freshly prepared compounds (**7b**, **7c** and **7j**) which exhibited excellent activity close to the standard antibiotic Streptomycin against GP and GN bacteria. Other compounds illustrated moderate activity. Compound (**7b**) indicated excellent activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus Subtilis*; Compound (**7c**) exhibited excellent activity against *S. aureus*. However, compound (**7i**) has outstanding activity against *Bacillus Subtilis* whereas compound (**7j**) demonstrated excellent activity against tabulated strains; *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus Subtilis* and *Salmonella*. The best action was seen against pathogens- *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus Subtilis* and *E.coli* and zone of inhibition was depicted in **Fig .12**

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of compounds(7a-7j)

Compounds	ZONE OF INHIBITION- mm			
	GP- <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	GP- <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	GN- <i>E.Coli</i>	GN- <i>Salmonella paratyphi</i>
7a	20	16	18	12
7b	24*	26*	09	15
7c	25*	13	23*	09
7d	12	12	15	10
7e	18	12	09	14
7f	20	17	16	09
7g	10	20	18	15
7h	09	26*	09	19
7i	13	24*	18	13
7j	26*	18	20	25*
Streptomycin	29	30	31	32

Fig 11: Graphical representation of Antibacterial activity of novel Schiff's bases of Indole-2-one derivatives(7a-7j)- Zone of Inhibition.

Fig12: Photograph showing zone of inhibition(mm) against bacterial strain *Salmonella paratyphi*

4.3. Structural Activity Relationship:

Structural activity relationship of the synthesized sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases (7a-7j) derivatives bearing N-substituted benzyl/4-methyl benzyl chloride and electron withdrawing, electron releasing groups at ortho/meta/para positions plays on magnificent role in the antibacterial, anticancer activities. Structure activity relationship for anti-cancer and anti-bacterial activity of newly synthesized sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases are shown in the **Fig:13**.

Fig13: SAR of Sulphonamide containing novel Schiff's bases of Indole-2-one derivatives.

- ✓ Replacement of aromatic ring in Benzene sulphonamide by other ring systems or the introduction of additional substituents at 2nd, 3rd/4th, 5th positions on it increases/abolish activity.
- ✓ When R/R₁/R₂ is substituted with phenyl, thiazole with methyl, Acetone groups activity is decreases, when it is may be EWGs or EDGs activity will be maximum.

- ✓ The novel indole-2-one molecules contains aromatic rings have been substituted with electron-withdrawing groups ($-\text{Cl}$, $-\text{NO}_2$) at P-position enhance the biological activities like anticancer and antimicrobial activities.

Fig 14: Positions of Active Substituents like Electron withdrawing groups

- ✓ Most of the synthesized compounds with para methyl (**7b**, **7g**, and **7j**) or methoxy group were more active (anticancer and antimicrobial) analogue's compare with unsubstituted derivatives (**7a**).

Fig 15 : Position of substituents R, R₁ and R₂ related to Pharmacological Activity

- ✓ Generally, tri substitution at on 'N' of benzene sulphonamide group leads to inactive.
- ✓ The C=N linkages between Indole with benzene sulphonamide is showing better activity than C-C/C=C linkages.

Fig 16: C=N linkage related to pharmacological activity

Secondary amine group (-NH) is essential for the activity and must be unsubstituted. If it is substituted with any group antimicrobial activity is lost.

**Insilco EGFR Inhibition of Sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases-
Glide- Dock score of the dataset Ligands.**

Compounds No	Dock Score	No of H-bonds	Amino acids (Interacted)	H-bond lengths (Å ⁰)	E-model energy	Binding energy
7b	-9.729	0	-	-	-50.179	-42.828
7c	-9.238	2	TRP 383 ARG 394	2.19 1.98	-54.806	-39.102
7d	-5.464	1	TRP 383	2.38	-41.963	-37.465
7e	-8.438	0	TRP 383	1.88	-39.581	-16.627
7g	-5.684	0	-	-	-56.759	-38.961
7h	-6.088	0	-	-	-54.235	-41.191
7j	-9.823	0	-	-	-59.274	-43.984
Doxorubicin	-6.781	4	LYS 721 ASP 831 CYS 773 ASP716	2.14 1.94 1.93 1.85	-55.203	-46.358

Fig 17: 7b-Docking Pose between the Ligand and the protein Dock-1 and Dock-2

Fig 18: 7c-Docking Pose between the Ligands and the Protein Dock-1 and Dock-2

Fig19: 7d- Docking pose between the Ligand and the Protein Dock-1 and Dock-2

Fig 20: 7e-Docking Pose between the Ligand and the Protein Dock-1 and Dock-2

Fig 21: 7g-Docking pose between the Ligand and the protein dock-1 and Dock-2

Fig 22: 7h- Docking pose between the Ligand and the Protein Dock-1 and Dock-2

4.4. Physical and Spectral data of Synthesized compounds(7a-7j)

4.4.1. (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-2-oxoindoin-3-ylidene)-benzene-sulfonohydrazide(7a).

Mol. Formula	: C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ S
Mol. Weight	: 391.10g/mol
Solubility	: Ethanol, Methanol, DMSO
Melting Point	: 183-185-1 ⁰ C
Percentage Yield	: 84%
Physical State	: Pale yellow crystals
IR-v cm⁻¹:	3293(-NH Str in NHSO ₂); 3036(-CH Str, Aro); 2929, 2832, 2832(-CH Str, Aliphatic); 1708(-CO Str, in Indole); 1614(-C=CH Str); 1476(-C=C Str in Aro); 1212(-SO ₂ Str); 1012(-CN Str).
¹HNMR (DMSO)δ ppm	: 9.8985(1H, s, sulphonamide proton); 9.2054(s, 2H, Benzyl proton); 8.0216-8.0021(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.9382-7.9023(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.8543-7.8142(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.7043-7.7002(t, 2H, Aro-H); 7.5864-7.5034(t, 3H, Aro-H); 7.4985-7.4697(t, 3H, Aro-H).
¹³C-NMR [[100 MHz, CDCl₃]]	: 173, 158, 146, 144, 140, 138, 133, 131, 129, 128, 126, 125, 123, 121, 118, 117, 42.
Mass -[[LC-MS]]	: m/z 391.13 (M); 392.03 (M+1).

4.4.2. (Z)-N¹-(benzyl-5-methyl-2-oxindolin-3ylidene)benzenesulfonohydrazide-(7b)

- Mol. Formula** : C₂₂H₁₉N₃O₃
- Mol. Weight** : 405.11g/mol
- Solubility** : Ethanol, Methanol, DMSO
- Melting Point** : 137-139⁰C
- Percentage Yield** : 81%
- Physical State** : Cream colour crystals
- IR ((ν cm⁻¹))** : 3242(-NH *Str* in NHSO₂); 3023(-CH *Str* in Aro); 2928, 2815(- CH *Str* in Aliphatic); 1708(-CO *Str* in Indole); 1612(-C=CH *Str*); 1480(-C=C *Str* in Aro-ring); 1286(-SO₂*Str*); 1013(-CN *Str*).
- ¹HNMR (DMSO) δ ppm**: 9.6754(s, 2H, Benzyl proton); 9.0455(s, 1H, sulphonamide proton); 8.0065(s, 2H, Aro-H); 7.9867-7.9653(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.7233-7.7003(t, 3H, Aro-H); 7.4998-7.4934(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.3985-7.3643(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.3082-7.3005(t, 2H, Aro-H); 2.0233(s, 3H, Aro-CH₃).
- ¹³C-NMR[[100 MHz, CDCl₃]]**: 175, 155, 144, 142 141, 136, 132, 130, 127, 124, 122, 120, 119, 117, 115, 113, 110, 48, 29.
- Mass -[[LC-MS]]** : m/z 405.11(M); 406.04(M+1).

4.4.3. (Z)-N¹-(1-benzyl-5-chloro-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene)-benzenesulfonohydrazide (7c)

Mol. Formula	:	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₃ S
Mol. Weight	:	425.06g/mol
Solubility	:	Ethanol, Methanol, DMSO
Melting Point	:	227-229 ⁰ C
Percentage Yield	:	86%
Physical State	:	Yellowish crystals
IR ((ν cm⁻¹))	:	3237(-NH Str in NHSO ₂); 3027(-CH Str, Ar); 2995, 2793(-CH Str, Aliphatic); 1709(-CO Str, Indole); 1612(-C=CH, Str); 1451(-C=C Str, Ar); 1251(SO ₂ Str); 1015(-C-N Str); 792(-Cl Str, Ar-Cl).
¹HNMR (DMSO) δ ppm	:	9.8543(s, 2H, Benzyl proton); 9.0053(s, 1H, sulphonamide proton); 8.1982(s, 1H, Ar-H); 8.2763-8.2193(d, 2H, Ar-H); 7.7564-7.7403(d, 2H, Ar-H); 7.6987-7.6798(d, 2H, Ar-H); 7.9109-7.9000(t, 3H, Ar-H); 7.5432-7.5219(t, 3H, Ar-H).
¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃)	:	171, 154, 143, 140 139, 137, 134, 133, 129, 125, 123, 122, 118, 115, 114, 111, 110, 48.
Mass (LC-MS)	:	m/z 425.06(M); 426.12(M+1); 427.03(M + 2).

4.4.4.: (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-5-nitro-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene)-benzenesulfonylhydrazide (7d).

- Mol. Formula** : C₂₂H₁₆N₄O₅S
- Mol. Weight** : 436.08g/mol
- Solubility** : Ethanol, Methanol, DMSO
- Melting Point** : 151-153⁰C
- Percentage Yield** : 79%
- Physical State** : Brown crystals
- IR ((ν cm⁻¹))** : 3362(-NH *Str* in NHSO₂); 3127(-CH *Str* in Aro); 2989, 2891, 2791(-C-H *Str* in Aliphatic group); 1719(-CO *Str* in Indole ring); 1614(-NO₂*Str* in Aro-NO₂); 1527(-C=CH *Str*); 1413(-C=C *Str* in Aromatic ring); 1291(-SO₂*Str*); 1012(-CN *Str*).
- ¹H NMR (DMSO) δ ppm** : 9.6993(s, 2H, Benzyl proton); 9.1231(s, 1H, sulphonamide proton); 8.3032(s, 1H, Aro-H); 7.9291-7.9002(t, 3H, Aro-H); 7.7998-7.7802(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.6675-7.6345(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.5875-7.5209(t, 3H, Aro-H); 7.4903-7.4564(d, 2H, Aro-H).
- ¹³C-NMR [[100 MHz, CDCl₃]]** : 178, 152, 146, 144, 143, 138, 134, 132, 128, 126, 124, 122, 120, 119, 117, 115, 114, 46.
- Mass -[[LC-MS]]**: m/z 436.08 (M); 437.21 (M+1)

4.4.5.(Z)-N'-(5-chloro-1-(4-methylbenzyl)-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene) benzene sulfonohydrazide (7e)

Mol. Formula	:	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₃ S
Mol. Weight	:	439.08g/mol
Solubility :		Ethanol, Methanol, DMSO
Melting Point	:	209-211 ⁰ C
Percentage Yield	:	84%
Physical State	:	Pale green crystals
IR ((ν cm⁻¹))	:	3234(-NH Str in NHSO ₂); 3028(-CH Str in Aro); 2993, 2872(-CH Str in Aliphatic); 1704(-CO Str in Indole); 1613(-C=CH Str); 1437(-C=C Str in Aromatic ring); 1225(-SO ₂ Str); 1116(-CN Str).
¹HNMR (DMSO) δ ppm:		9.7998(s, 2H, Benzyl proton); 9.0934(s, 1H, sulphonamide proton); 8.3098(s, 1H, Aro-H); 7.9132-7.8009(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.7989-7.7675(t, 3H, Aro-H); 7.6281-7.6002(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.5945-7.5123(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.4985-7.4102(d, 2H, Aro-H), 2.031 (s, 3H, -CH ₃).
¹³C-NMR[[100 MHz,CDCl₃]] :		173, 154, 148, 144, 143, 138, 135, 134, 132, 130, 128, 125, 122, 120, 119, 118, 45, 27.
Mass -[[LC-MS]]-	:	m/z 439.03(M); 440.02(M+1); 441.03(M+2).

4.4.6:(Z)-N'-(1-(4-methylbenzyl)-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzenesulfonohydrazide (7f)

- Mol. Formula** : C₂₂H₁₉N₃O₃S
- Mol. Weight** : 405.11g/mol
- Solubility** : Ethanol, Methanol, DMSO
- Melting Point** : 223-225⁰C
- Percentage Yield** : 76%
- Physical State** : White crystals
- IR ((ν cm⁻¹))** : 3298(-NH *Str* in NHSO₂); 3098(-CH *Str*, Ar); 2976, 2898, 2765(-CH *Str* in Aliphatic); 1720(-CO *Str* in Indole); 1599(-C=CH, *Str*); 1423(-C=C *Str* in Ar); 1256(-SO₂ *Str*); 1034(-C-N *Str*).
- ¹HNMR (DMSO) δ ppm:** 9.6854(s, 2H, Benzyl proton); 9.1293(s, 1H, sulphonamide proton); 8.1023-8.0343(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.9983-7.9329(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.6832-7.5643(t, 3H, Aro-H); 7.4892-7.3984(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.2097-7.1563(d, 2H, Aro-H); 6.9874-6.9002(t, 2H, Aro-H), 2.103 (s, 3H, -CH₃).
- ¹³C-NMR[[100 MHz, CDCl₃]]:**170, 158, 142, 140, 139, 137, 135, 133, 132, 130, 128, 126, 1234, 123, 120, 118, 112, 43, 22.
- Mass -[[LC-MS]]** : m/z 405.11(M); 406.23(M+1).

4.4.7. (Z)-N'-(1-(4-methoxybenzyl)-5-nitro-2-oxindolin -3-ylidene-sulfonohydrazide (7g)

- Mol. Formula** : C₂₂H₁₈N₄O₅S
- Mol. Weight** : 450.10g/mol
- Solubility** : Ethanol, Methanol, DMSO
- Melting Point** : 147-149⁰C
- Percentage Yield** : 69%
- Physical State** : Yellow crystals
- IR ((ν cm⁻¹))** : 3287(-NH *Str* in NHSO₂); 3084(-CH *Str* in Aro); 2994, 2854, 2787(-CH *Str* in Aliphatic); 1713(-CO *Str* in Indole); 1623(-NO₂*Str* in Aro-NO₂); 1602(-C=CH, *Str*); 1446(-C=C *Str* in Ar); 1293(-SO₂ *Str*); 1045(-C-N *Str*).
- ¹HNMR (DMSO) δ ppm**: 9.8754(s, 2H, Benzyl proton); 9.2934(s, 1H, sulphonamide proton); 8.3233(s, 1H, Aro-H); 8.1204-8.1004(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.9843-7.9032(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.8943-7.7893(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.6743-7.5893(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.2203-7.1893(t, 3H, Aro-H), 2.113 (s, 3H, -CH₃).
- ¹³C-NR[[100 MHz, CDCl₃]]** : **172**; 156, 147, 143, 142, 137, 134, 133, 130, 126, 124, 122, 120, 119, 117, 115, 113, 49, 28.
- Mass – [[LC-MS]]** : m/z 450.10 (M); 451.02 (M+1).

4.4.8. (Z)-N'-(5-methyl-1-(4-methylbenzyl)-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzene sulfonohydrazide (7h)

- Mol. Formula** : C₂₃H₂₁N₃O₃S
- Mol. Weight** : 419.13g/mol
- Solubility** : Ethanol, Methanol, DMSO
- Melting Point** : 236-238⁰C
- Percentage Yield** : 77%
- Physical State** : Cream colour crystals
- IR ((ν cm⁻¹))** : 3284(-NH *Str* in NHSO₂); 3065(-CH *Str* in Ar); 2987, 2865, 2761(-CH *Str* in Aliphatic); 1708(-CO *Str* in Indole); 1543(-C=CH, *Str*); 1419(-C=C *Str* in Ar); 1304(SO₂ *Str*); 1023(-C-N *Str*).
- ¹HNMR (DMSO) δ ppm**: 9.5674(s, 2H, Benzyl proton); 9.0932(s, 1H, sulphonamide proton); 8.2093(s, 1H, Aro-H); 8.0934-8.0041(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.8943-7.7343(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.6584-7.6002(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.5232-7.5032(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.3982-7.2093(t, 3H, Aro-H), 2.2093(s, 3H, Aro-CH₃); 1.9982(s, 3H, Aro-CH₃).
- ¹³C-NM[[100 MHz, CDCl₃]]** : 176, 159, 148, 146, 145, 141, 138, 135, 132, 129, 126, 124, 122, 120, 118, 115, 112, 46, 27, 25.
- Mass -[[LC-MS]]** : m/z 419.13 (M); 420.18 (M+1).

4.4.9. (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene)-4-methylbenzene sulfonohydrazide (7i)

- Mol. Formula** : C₂₂H₁₉N₃O₃S
- Mol. Weight** : 405.11g/mol
- Solubility** : Ethanol, Methanol, DMSO
- Melting Point** : 261-263⁰C
- Percentage Yield** : 86%
- Physical State** : White crystals
- IR ((ν cm⁻¹))** : 3286(-NH *Str* in NHSO₂); 3094(-CH *Str* in Ar); 2967, 2804(-CH *Str* in Aliphatic); 1703(-CO *Str* in Indole); 1513(-C=CH *Str*); 1409(-C=C *Str* in Aromatic group); 1287(SO₂*Str*); 1102(-CN *Str*).
- ¹HNMR (DMSO) δ ppm:** 9.8032(s, 2H, Benzyl proton); 9.2019(s, 1H, sulphonamide proton); 8.2093-8.0182(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.7834-7.7102(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.5983-7.5192(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.3982-7.3102(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.1982-7.1352(t, 3H, Aro-H); 7.1024-7.0232(t, 2H, Aro-H), 2.108(s, 3H, -CH₃).
- ¹³C-NMR[[100 MHz, CDCL₃]]:**177, 156, 148, 146, 144, 142, 135, 133, 130, 129, 125, 123, 120, 119, 117, 115, 47, 26, 21.
- Mass -[[LC-MS]]** : m/z 405.11 (M); 406 (M+1).

4.5.10.-: (Z)-N-(1-benzyl-5-methyl-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene)-methylbenzene-sulfonamide (7j)

- Mol. Formula** : C₂₃H₂₁N₃O₃S
- Mol. Weight** : 419.13g/mol
- Solubility** : Ethanol, Methanol, DMSO
- Melting Point** : 187-189⁰C
- Percentage Yield** : 78%
- Physical State** : Brown crystals
- IR ((ν cm⁻¹))** : 3278(-NH *Str* in NHSO₂); 3092(-CH *Str* in Aro); 2943, 2878, 2784(-CH *Str* in Aliphatic); 1710(-CO *Str* in Indole); 1523(-C=CH, *Str*); 1424(-C=C *Str* in Ar); 1287(SO₂ *Str*); 1078(-C-N *Str*).
- ¹HNMR (DMSO) δ ppm:** 9.8032(s, 2H, Benzyl proton); 9.1092(s, 1H, sulphonamide proton); 8.3092(s, 1H, Aro-H); 8.1093-8.0002(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.9843-7.8733(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.7833-7.6985(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.3764-7.2091(d, 2H, Aro-H); 7.1523-7.1093(t, 3H, Aro-H); 2.3092(s, 3H, Aro-CH₃); 2.0933(s, 3H, Aro-CH₃).
- ¹³C-NMR[[100 MHz, CDCl₃]]:** 174, 158, 145, 143, 142, 141, 136, 134, 132, 130, 128, 124, 123, 122, 120, 119, 49, 28, 25.
- Mass -[[LC-MS]]** : m/z 419.13(M); 420.23(M+1)

4.5. Conclusion:

In the present investigation is focused on the synthesis, characterization of sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases (**7a-7j**) and biological activities (antibacterial and anticancer). The compound **7a**, **7c** and **7j** showed good antibacterial activity against *staphylococcus aureus*, *E. Coli* bacteria. Compounds **7b** and **7c** showed acceptable activity towards the cell lines, other synthesized compounds reports tolerable activity. Further, the molecular docking study of the target data set of sulphonamide containing novel Indole-2-one Schiff's bases was performed by Schrodinger Suite. In Molecular docking studies, Compound **7b** has reported highest dock score **-9.729** with binding energy **-42.828 Kcal/mol**, compound **7c**-dock score **-9.238**, compound **7e** -dock score **-8.438** and compound **7j**- dock score **-9.823** has also reported highest dock score compared to the standard drug. Dock - scores of all the freshly developed compounds reported at **-8.512 (8a) to -3.142 (8c)**. Most of the docked compounds did not possess substantial H-bond interactions. H-bonds were recorded only between compounds **7e** (GLY 521), **7i** (LEU 525), **7j** (ASP 351), **7f** (ASP 351) and the protein binding site. Protein residues such as ARG 394 and TRP 383 had shown hydrophobic interactions with compounds **7d** and **7c**; TRP 383 had significant hydrophobic interactions with compounds **7g**, **8e**, **7d** and **7e**

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SPECTRAL DATA

Fig 23: Mass Spectra of (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzenesulfonylhydrazide (7a)

Fig 24: Mass Spectra of (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-5-methyl-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzenesulfonylhydrazide(7b)

Fig 25: Mass spectra of (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-5-chloro-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzenesulfonylhydrazide(7c)

Fig 26 : Mass Spectra of (Z)-N'-(1-(4-methyl)-benzyl-5-chloro-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzenesulfonylhydrazide(7e)

Fig 28 : ¹H NMR Spectra of (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-5-chloro-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzenesulfonylhydrazide (7c)

Fig 30 : ¹H NMR Spectra of (Z)-N'-(5-chloro-1-(4-methylbenzyl)-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene) benzene sulfonylhydrazide (7e)

Fig 31: IR Spectra of (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzenesulfonohydrazide (7a)

Fig 32: IR Spectra of (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-5-methyl-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzenesulfonohydrazide(7b)

Fig 33: IR Spectra of (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-5-chloro-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzenesulfonylhydrazide (7c)

Fig 34: IR Spectra of (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-5-nitro-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)benzenesulfonylhydrazide(7d)

Fig 35: IR Spectra of (Z)-N'-(5-chloro-1-(4-methylbenzyl)-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene) benzene sulfonohydrazide (7e)

Fig 36 : ^{13}C spectra of (Z)-N-(1-benzyl-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)-benzene-sulfonohydrazide(7a).

Fig 38: ^{13}C NMR Spectra of (Z)-N'-(1-benzyl-2-oxindolin-3ylidene)-4-methylbenzene sulfonylhydrazide (7i)

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